

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D8.3

Overall Project Results Ratified by OEM

 <https://xrotor-project.eu>

 @XROTORProject

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Author(s)	James Carroll (University of Strathclyde) Jordi Jove Bellow (GE)

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X-ROTOR Consortium

University of Strathclyde

Delft University of Technology

University College Cork – National University of Ireland, Cork

Fundacion Cener

General Electric Renovables España

Norwegian University of Science and Technology

CENER

NTNU - Trondheim
Norwegian University of
Science and Technology

UCC
Coláiste na hOllscoile Corcaigh, Éire
University College Cork, Ireland

<https://xrotor-project.eu>

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

1 Introduction and Description of the Deliverable

This deliverable consists of a summary of the results from the XROTOR reviewed and ratified by OEM. Whilst a summary of the results from each Work Package are shown in this document an expanded overview can be seen in D1.6 and full results can be seen in the deliverables associated with each Work Package. Work packages 1 and 8 are not included in this deliverable as they were project management and governance related work packages. The purpose of this deliverable is to briefly summarise the XROTOR project results and evidence the fact that they have been reviewed ratified by a wind turbine OEM. This deliverable will be considered successfully complete when the report is sent to the project coordinator.

List of acronyms

VAWT	Vertical Axis Wind Turbine
HAWT	Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine
PMSG	Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator
UoS	University of Strathclyde
UCC	University College Cork
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
TU Delft	Delft University of Technology
CENER	National Renewable Energy Centre

2 Work Package 2 Summary: Aero-elastic code development and performance. Completed by TU Delft & CENER

The goals of WP2 “Aero-elastic code development and performance” were to create an aero-elastic dynamic model of the X-Rotor concept; a CFD prediction tool to validate the aeroelastic computations; test a small-scale X-Rotor concept in a wind tunnel; to evaluate the loading and performance of a full-scale X-Rotor concept; to predict noise emissions from the X-Rotor concept by CFD simulations; and to complete Multibody analysis of the X-Rotor Concept. Exceeding the initial project scope, WP2 also demonstrated the innovative concept of Regenerative Wind Farming with the X-Rotor, both numerically and experimentally, through multiple wind tunnel tests and simulations.

The benchmarking of aerodynamic simulations corroborated the consistency across different models concerning the loads and power curves of the X-Rotor, including aspects of control operations. Notably, the simulation benchmarks confirmed a consensus regarding the X-Rotor's ability to achieve a high-power coefficient; specifically, the main rotor attained a power coefficient exceeding 0.46, approximately 20% higher than conservative projections outlined in the original project proposal. Noise emission studies revealed that while the primary rotor maintained low noise levels, the secondary rotors emitted considerable noise at specific frequencies, indicating the need for further refinement in design and analysis.

The multi-fidelity aeroelastic analysis across various models showed strong agreement. The load cases identified were subsequently integrated into the control studies of Work Package 3 (WP3), with no critical impediments identified to the design and operation.

Experimental validations conducted in wind tunnels utilized multiple models, including proof-of-concept of the X-Rotor configurations with secondary rotors. Loads and flow fields were measured in detail, and the data was used in the validation of different models. In addition, wake and wind farm (array) were tested in the wind tunnel. These tests not only verified the wake control strategies inherent to the Regenerative Wind Farming concept but also demonstrated their efficacy in both single and nine-turbine array configurations. Flow and load measurements validated the anticipated power gains and confirmed the capability of large-scale entrainment of energy in downstream turbines, doubling the energy available for downwind turbines. This result opens new possibilities for the X-Rotor, suggesting potentially higher wind farm efficiency compared with current Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine Technology.

3 Work Package 3 Summary: Operational Strategy and Control. Completed by University of Strathclyde

The overall objective for WP3 is to determine the most appropriate operating strategy for the X-Rotor, that maximises energy capture within load limits, and to design the controller for the X-Rotor to realise them. The key results achieved in meeting this objective are summarised below. An

operational strategy has been determined that optimises energy capture whilst ensuring that power take-off can be accomplished through the secondary rotors by direct drive with standard generators. Appropriate control simulation and control design models have been developed. The control simulation model includes the following elements, a three-dimensional representation of the wind field that is sufficiently detailed that forces and moments induced on the primary and secondary rotors are reasonably accurate up to 6P, aerodynamic models for the primary and secondary rotors, structural models of the primary rotor that includes the dominant blade modes and power take-off models that includes their secondary rotors and generators. The primary rotor control design model is simplified by removing the azimuthal dependent aspects of both the primary and secondary rotors. In addition, the structural dynamics of the primary rotor is simplified by considering the lower half of the primary rotor to be rigid and both upper blades to have a single dynamic model. The secondary rotor control design model is, except for some minor modifications, the same as the that incorporated into the control simulation model. Linearised versions of the primary and secondary rotor design models suitable for controller design have been determined.

Controllers have been designed using the control design models for all operating conditions, namely, very low wind speeds when the secondary rotors are regulated to operate at constant rotor speed, low wind speeds when the secondary rotors are regulated to operate at the optimal power coefficient, intermediate wind speeds when the primary rotor blades are pre-emptively pitched during transition to above rated operation and above rated wind speeds when the primary rotor blades are pitched to maintain near constant speed and torque/power. The performance of the controller has been assessed using the control simulation model for a series of wind conditions, namely, for below rated wind speeds with mean 7m/s, 8m/s and 9m/s, intermediate wind speed with mean 11.5m/s and above rated wind speeds with mean 14m/s, 17m/s, 20m/s and 23m/s.

4 Work Package 4 Summary: Design of mechanical structure and analysis. Completed by NTNU

The goal of WP4 “Design of mechanical structure and analysis” has been to design the mechanical structure of the X-Rotor for a relevant offshore site. Focusing on the most important components, a complete structural design of the crossbar, shaft, bearings, tower, and jacket support structure, including soil piles, has been obtained and the initial blade design has been checked and slightly improved. The structural design has been performed in accordance with industry guidelines and international design standards and shown to satisfy the relevant criteria for structural safety. The final substructure is relatively heavy and costly compared to designs of horizontal-axis wind turbines, but this is not unexpected for such a concept with a primary vertical-axis rotor that has no load reducing control strategy. Overall, the feasibility of the concept has been demonstrated, but it is also clear that in its configuration as a two-bladed turbine, optimized mainly for power production, the concept is not well balanced and is not economically optimal. Major additional findings of this work package are that the structural cost depends almost linearly on the rotor loads, which defines a clear pathway toward further optimization of the concept. In fact, our results suggest that a three-bladed X-Rotor with a more damage-conscious controller would reduce the structural cost by more than half. Apart

from providing a baseline structural design of the concept, this work package has also developed new ideas and approaches for structural optimization of wind turbine jackets and made some important theoretical advancements. Full details on the WP4 work can be seen in the WP4 deliverables.

5 Work Package 5 Summary: Power take-off and conversion system design. Completed by University of Strathclyde

The WP5 of XROTOR Project has completed in three stages successfully, focusing on various aspects of Power take-off and conversion system design.

The project included detailed analysis and design of Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generators (PMSG) to meet operational strategies, structural limitations, and operational ranges. The optimal design for 690V and 3.3KV PMSG machines was developed using meta heuristic optimization algorithms and design methodologies created by experts in machine design. Electric performance analysis was conducted under steady state and extreme operation conditions (i.e. maximum loading and over-speeding) using finite element analysis, confirming the suitability of the chosen generator and power electronic converter configuration for the system. The optimization algorithm was also capable of designing inner or outer rotor machines. This provided a new degree of flexibility in the thermal management of the secondary rotor design. Using the developed machine design algorithms, mechanical design and final element analysis, a solution to dissipate heat using outer rotor configuration and metallic blades in the secondary rotors was proposed to avoid the use of generator surface fins that reduce aerodynamic efficiency.

The power electronic architecture for the generators was selected as 3-level converters with voltage and current handling levels that allowed the overloading and over-speeding of the secondary rotors. Transferring power from generators placed on the rotating structure of the X-rotor could use slip rings or a wireless power transfer element. With the aim to understand the implications of using a wireless power system, the project designed a rotary transformer (RT) system for wireless power transfer, capable of handling the MW power transfer requirement of the XROTOR system. Detailed specifications and efficiency analysis were provided, along with the design and analysis of a suitable power electronic topology for the RT. A three-phase dual active bridge configuration was proposed to handle the power transfer between the terminal of the RT system, demonstrating efficiency levels of around 98% for 5-MW-level power transfer. Detailed analysis of the cost of the wireless power solution vs conventional slip ring technology was carried out from an operational and cost analysis perspective.

The final stage addressed improvements and control of the XROTOR power take-off system, including the PMSG, generator-side power electronics, RT system, and grid-side converter. A full controller design and analysis of the XROTOR drivetrain were presented, including controllers for the generator converters, dual active bridge converter, and grid-side converter. The power electronic architecture was optimized to minimize the size of the power electronic devices in two out of the three electrical energy conversion stages in the drive train, allowing savings in cost. The designed controller structure, consisting of 11 different controllers, was found capable of stable operation for energy conversion and transmission through the XROTOR system. The combined efficiency of the RT and the dual active bridge converter was reported as 96%, meeting the project's efficiency goals. The design of controllers used novel techniques such as two degrees of freedom internal model controllers for improved robustness performance.

6 Work Package 6 Summary: O&M and LCoE Modelling and Analysis. Completed by University of Strathclyde and UCC

WP6 results showed that the X-Rotor concept is anticipated to yield significant maintenance cost savings for wind turbines, in addition to capital cost reductions. The work package focused on quantifying these savings to assess the X-Rotor's overall cost-effectiveness compared to traditional horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTs). The University of Strathclyde developed a maintenance cost model tailored to the X-Rotor's unique characteristics, which projected a reduction in maintenance costs by 21-45% compared to traditional turbines due to greatly reduced use of jack up vessels and the removal of high downtime and high failure rate components such as the gearbox and multipole generator. A LCoE model created by UCC, which integrated the previously mentioned O&M cost model, estimated potential savings of 10-19% in the cost of generating wind energy. These numbers are based on the wind turbine, not the associated balance of plant. This LCoE saving is driven by the O&M cost savings mentioned above but also by the capital cost savings from not having a gearbox or multipole generator. Further design advancements, especially related to the primary rotor, are expected to elevate these savings beyond 20%. The WP 6 analysis underscores the X-Rotor's promise in enhancing wind energy affordability and sustainability. Further details on the WP6 results can be seen in D6.1, D6.2 and D6.3.

7 Work Package 7 Summary: Social, economic and environmental impact of the X-Rotor. Completed by University College Cork

The objective of WP7 was to assess and mitigate the social, economic and environmental impact of the X-Rotor Concept (XRC), and to establish noise levels for environmental impact studies. To this end the WP was structured into three tasks. The first task focused on the social acceptability of X-Rotor engaging with stakeholders to ensure that their perceptions and opinions informed the development of the novel turbine. The societal stakeholders proved open to the X-Rotor concept but indicated a number of concerns particularly around potential impacts on land and sea traffic and potential impact to local fisheries. Industrial stakeholders on the other hands were more focused on the potential performance of X-Rotor, in terms such as LCOE, durability, etc.

The second task was concerned with the economic implications of X-Rotor and its deployment, especially in comparison to conventional horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTs). An input-output analysis was used to examine the differential effect of X-Rotor and HAWTs on jobs, earnings, economic value added and total output for hypothetical deployments in Ireland, Spain, and the UK. This showed that the effect depended on the existing availability of industries to build the X-Rotor components and on the size of the economies studied. A second economic analysis took a system wide perspective using a computable general equilibrium model to examine the differential effects on the whole of the UK economy with various levels of uptake of X-Rotor. This showed a larger positive effect on gross domestic product compared with the input-output analysis as it included

internal effects of lower energy prices within the economy, something beyond the scope of the input output model. Both approaches estimated very similar effects on jobs.

The final task explored the environmental aspects of X-Rotor, in particular examining the impact sea birds. Through a combination of desk research and primary data collection, Collision and Displacement Vulnerability Indices were developed to assess the most at-risk species to wind turbines. These were combined with seabird distribution data to generate vulnerability maps for breeding, wintering and migration periods when risk is likely to vary. This work showed that auks, loons and ducks are highly vulnerable to displacement while some procellariiforms and larids are vulnerable to collision with wind turbines. The work showed that vulnerability to collision and displacement at the seabird community level are not evenly distributed and vary with season according to the distribution of the most at-risk species. Finally, the vulnerability maps indicated areas of higher vulnerability at the European scale, highlighting where further surveys, monitoring, tracking studies, or mitigation might be needed. Related work assessed the noise impact of the X-Rotor on the seabirds. Noise emission from X-Rotor under maximum power extraction were found to be significantly lower than the harmful threshold and unlikely to trigger any response behaviour from sea birds.

8 Work Package 9 summary: Communication and Dissemination. Completed by University College Cork

At the commencement of the project, a visual identity was developed for use within X-Rotor. This included high resolutions versions of project logo, funding acknowledgements, presentation templates, report templates, display banners, and posters. These were distributed to the project partners for their use in the realisation of the project.

A website – <https://xrotor-project.eu> – was designed and prepared for the project, it went live on 31-March-2021. The objectives of the website were to: raise awareness about the project and its objectives; communicate about the project’s research and outreach activities; promote engagement with industry and societal stakeholders; disseminate the results of the project; and acknowledge funding and support of the Horizon 2020 programme; and publicise the involvement of the participating partners (and where appropriate, individual contributors). The project website was designed and maintained using the WordPress Content Management System (CMS). A feature-rich CMS that allows the development of quite complex sites, but allows non-expert users to substantially maintain the site. A modern responsive web design approach was taken, meaning that the coding is such that the website is presented differently depending on the viewing device. This is so that content will be resized or hidden in accordance with the formatting and presentation layers protocols on device of different sizes i.e., desktops, tablets, and smartphones. The website was initially ‘soft-launched’ with a simple layout before being revamped and redesigned (with video mock-ups of the X-Rotor), once feedback was gathered from critical friends¹. The website has a relatively straightforward structure comprising the following: landing page, overview of the project, profile of partners, project outputs, news and events, contact details. Over the life of the project the website was

updated. Many of these sections (e.g., project outputs) had minimal content at the start, which was added to as the project progressed.

Once research outputs started to emerge, a Zenodo presence was established for the project on <https://zenodo.org/communities/x-rotor>. All project outputs are deposited in this general open access repository. Public deliverables and open access publications are freely available, while confidential deliverables have restricted access. The repository provides DOIs for documents (if required), which greatly improves the ability to cite X-Rotor outputs making it easier to promote the research. This use of the Zenodo repository, provided through the EU OpenAire initiative, will ensure the availability of project outputs long after the project has concluded².

The project also had a presence on social media, specifically Twitter (or X as it become known). The account established at the start of the project (@XRotorProject) was utilised in a supporting role to other communication channels. It was used to promote the project, highlight partners and their contributions, and as a means to promote project outputs. Towards the latter stages of the project a project YouTube channel was established as a means of sharing videography from X-Rotor – <https://www.youtube.com/@XROTORProject>. While never intended as a major route for project communications, it does offer a means of documenting events and communicating outputs from the project.

Newsletters were prepared during focused on specific themes of the project, these were made available through the project website. The first served as an introduction to, and an over of the X-Rotor project. The other newsletters covered a range of themes including: economic analyses, societal and human aspects, environmental aspects,

To promote the work of the project and disseminate emerging results, three X-Rotor mini-symposia organised as official components of major research conferences. In January 2023, an X-Rotor mini-symposium was organised during EERA DeepWind 2023 conference in Trondheim, Norway. While in May 2023, a second X-Rotor mini-symposium was organised during the Wind Energy Science Conference 2023 held in Glasgow, United Kingdom.

In March 2024, a final project mini-symposia was held in the context of the WindEurope Annual Event in Bilbao, Spain. The seminar comprised two segments, a morning session which provided a high-level overview of the project and the research undertaken, and an afternoon session which delved more deeply into a number of technical aspects of the project through a combination of oral and poster presentations.

At the time of writing (22 April 2024), X-Rotor has resulted in the following publications. Eleven open access articles arising from the research conducted in the X-Rotor project published in, or submitted to, journals such as Journal of Physics: Conference Series; Open Research Europe; Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews; Wind Energy Science; Wind Energy. Five additional open access journal articles in preparation.

Twenty-five papers presented orally at conferences including EERA JP Wind-SP4; FALCON 30/50 Workshop: Future of Aerodynamics, Loads and Control 2030-2050 ; NAWEA WindTech Conference 2022; 6th IEEE Workshop on Electrical Machines Design, Control and Diagnosis WEMDCD 2023; 14th International Conference on Electromechanical and Energy Systems SIEMEN 2023; Wake Conference 2023; 20th International Symposium on Flow Visualization ISFV 2023; NAWEA WindTech Conference 2023; 10th International Conference on Wind Turbine Noise; EERA DeepWind 2023 Offshore Wind Conference; Wind Energy Science Conference 2023; EERA DeepWind 2024 Offshore Wind Conference; Torque 2024.

Four poster presentations at conferences such as: JM Burgers Symposium 2022; Wind Energy Ireland 2022; IEEE International Magnetic Conference INTERMAG 2023

9 Conclusion

The XROTOR project was made possible by collaborative efforts across partner institutions on 9 work packages. Through rigorous research, experimentation, and analysis, the project progressed the development and validation of the X-Rotor concept taking the concept from TRL 1 to TRL 3 during the 3 year 4-month project period.

One of the project's major achievements lies in the successful WP2 aerodynamic analysis of the X-Rotor concept. That work, bolstered by CFD predictions and wind tunnel tests, has and will provide valuable insights into the performance and loading characteristics of the X-Rotor. The validation of wake control strategies and the demonstration of potential efficiency gains through Regenerative Wind Farming attest to the concept's promise in enhancing wind farm productivity and viability for high density wind farms.

Furthermore, the design and analysis conducted in Work Packages 3, 4 and 5 have created new tools and yielded crucial insights into the X-Rotor's operation strategy, controller, mechanical structure, power take-off, and conversion system. While initial structural designs met industry standards, opportunities for optimization have been identified, paving the way for potential cost reductions and performance enhancements. Similarly, the detailed analysis and design of power take-off systems have ensured the compatibility, efficiency, and reliability of the X-Rotor's energy conversion mechanisms.

The economic analyses conducted in Work Package 6 have underscored the cost-effectiveness and competitiveness of the X-Rotor compared to traditional horizontal axis wind turbines. Projections of maintenance cost savings and reductions in the levelized cost of energy (LCoE) highlight the X-Rotor's potential to impact the wind energy landscape, offering both economic and environmental benefits. Moreover, the comprehensive assessment of social, economic, and environmental impacts conducted in Work Package 7 has provided invaluable insights into stakeholder perceptions, economic implications, and environmental considerations associated with the X-Rotor's deployment.

In addition to technical advancements, the X-Rotor project has been active in communication, dissemination, and knowledge exchange. The establishment of a project website, presence on social media platforms, organization of mini-symposia, and publication of research outputs have facilitated the dissemination of findings and engagement with stakeholders. These efforts have not only fostered collaboration within the research community but also raised awareness about the project's objectives, outcomes, and potential societal benefits.

10 Sign off /Ratification of Results from GE

GE confirm have been involved in the technical management of this X-Rotor research project, have taken part in design reviews, have reviewed the project results and are satisfied that the level of work completed is acceptable to a Wind turbine manufacturer/OEM.

Signature of X-Rotor Lead for GE:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'Jordi Jove Bellot', written on a light gray background.

Jordi Jove Bellot